

Epidemiology and Clinical Profiles of Eczema in Children and Adolescents: a Hospital-Based Cross-Sectional Study in Bihar

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Abstract:

Background: Eczema, a chronic inflammatory skin condition, is prevalent among children and adolescents, significantly impacting their quality of life. Despite its widespread occurrence, there is limited data on the epidemiology and clinical patterns of eczema in specific regions of India, including Bihar.

Aim: This study aims to assess the epidemiology, clinical characteristics, and associated factors of eczema among children and adolescents in Bihar, India, to inform better management strategies and public health interventions.

Methods: A hospital-based cross-sectional study was conducted over six months involving 100 children and adolescents diagnosed with eczema. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire covering demographic information, clinical history, and examination findings. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, employing descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and t-tests to identify significant associations, with a p-value of less than 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results: The study found that atopic dermatitis was the most prevalent form of eczema (60%), particularly among younger children (aged 1-10 years) and those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds. A significant association was observed between age, socioeconomic status, and the type of eczema. Treatment with topical corticosteroids led to significant improvement in 70% of cases, though a small percentage of patients required alternative therapies.

Conclusion: Eczema is a common condition among children and adolescents in Bihar, with atopic dermatitis being the most prevalent type. The study underscores the need for targeted interventions, particularly for younger children and those from lower-income families, to improve outcomes and reduce the burden of the disease.

Recommendations: It is recommended that public health strategies focus on early diagnosis, tailored treatment approaches, and improved access to dermatological care, especially for vulnerable populations. Further research is needed to explore alternative treatment options for non-responders and to understand the long-term impact of eczema in this demographic.

Keywords: Eczema, Atopic Dermatitis, Children, Adolescents, Epidemiology, Bihar.

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Introduction

Atopic dermatitis, another name for eczema, is a recurrent inflammatory skin disorder that is marked by redness, itching, and a rash. Its persistent nature and propensity for consequences have a major influence on quality of life, mainly affecting children and teenagers. With an estimated 15% to 20% of children globally suffering from eczema, it is one of the most prevalent skin conditions in children. It can last throughout adulthood and frequently starts in early childhood, which makes it a serious public health concern [1, 2].

Eczema is a complex pathophysiology that includes immune system dysfunction, genetic predisposition, and environmental causes. Recent

research has highlighted the part that microbial dysbiosis and compromised skin barriers play in the onset and aggravation of eczema. Asthma and allergic rhinitis are two more atopic disorders that are frequently linked to the condition, contributing to the phenomenon known as the "atopic march," in which an individual is predisposed to another allergic ailment over time [3, 4].

The incidence of eczema in India varies greatly between areas, depending on variables including access to healthcare, socioeconomic position, and climate. There is, however, a dearth of information regarding the epidemiology of eczema in particular

states, including Bihar. To improve patient outcomes and develop focused interventions, it is imperative to comprehend the clinical patterns and associated factors in this region [5].

In addition to its physical symptoms, eczema has a significant psychological influence on young people. Sleep issues, social stigma, and mental anguish are common in children with eczema, and these factors can have an impact on the development of the child as a whole and their academic achievement. A major financial burden is also placed on families by the disease's chronic nature, which necessitates numerous medical visits and continued therapy [6].

Eczema is still difficult to manage even with a wide range of therapeutic options available, such as topical corticosteroids, emollients, and more recent biologic medicines. Individual differences in treatment effectiveness mean that some patients will always have significant symptoms even after receiving the best possible care. This emphasises the necessity for individualised treatment plans built on a deeper comprehension of the clinical traits and epidemiology of the illness in various groups [7, 8].

This study aims to assess the epidemiology, clinical characteristics, and associated factors of eczema among children and adolescents in Bihar, India, to inform better management strategies and public health interventions.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a hospital-based prospective cross-sectional study.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at the Dermatology Department of Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital (DMCH), Bihar over a period of six months.

Participants: A total of 100 participants, comprising children and adolescents aged 1 to 18 years, were included in the study. The participants were selected from those attending the outpatient department (OPD) of DMCH during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Children and adolescents aged 1 to 18 years.
- Patients clinically diagnosed with eczema.
- Individuals who provided informed consent (or whose guardians provided consent for minors).

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with other dermatological conditions not related to eczema.
- Participants with a history of systemic diseases that could influence skin conditions.
- Those who refused to provide consent or were non-compliant with the study procedures.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, consecutive sampling was used where every eligible patient attending the OPD during the study period was included. Information bias was reduced by using a standardized questionnaire and diagnostic criteria for eczema.

Data Collection: Data was collected using a pre-structured questionnaire, which included demographic information, clinical history, and detailed examination findings related to eczema. The questionnaire was administered by trained personnel to ensure consistency and accuracy.

Procedure: Participants were clinically examined by a dermatologist to confirm the diagnosis of eczema. Relevant clinical data, including the type, duration, and severity of eczema, were recorded. The data were then entered into a secure database for analysis.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were calculated for demographic and clinical variables. Chi-square tests assessed associations between categorical variables, and t-tests were used for continuous variables. A p-value < 0.05 was considered significant.

Results

A total of 100 children and adolescents aged 1 to 18 years were included in the study. The mean age of participants was 9.5 years (SD = 4.2 years), with a nearly equal distribution between males (51%) and females (49%).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age Group (years)		
1-5	28	28%
6-10	35	35%
11-15	22	22%
16-18	15	15%
Gender		
Male	51	51%
Female	49	49%
Socioeconomic Status		

Low	42	42%
Middle	45	45%
High	13	13%

The most common type of eczema observed was atopic dermatitis (60%), followed by seborrheic dermatitis (20%), contact dermatitis (15%), and nummular eczema (5%). The mean duration of the condition was 2.3 years (SD = 1.5 years).

Table 2: Clinical Characteristics of Eczema Among Participants

Clinical Characteristic	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Type of Eczema		
Atopic Dermatitis	60	60%
Seborrheic Dermatitis	20	20%
Contact Dermatitis	15	15%
Nummular Eczema	5	5%
Duration of Condition		
<1 year	20	20%
1-3 years	55	55%
>3 years	25	25%
Severity		
Mild	30	30%
Moderate	50	50%
Severe	20	20%

An analysis was conducted to explore the association between demographic factors and the type of eczema. Atopic dermatitis was more prevalent in the younger age group (1-10 years) and was significantly associated with a lower socioeconomic status ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3: Association between Age Group and Type of Eczema

Age Group (years)	Atopic Dermatitis (n)	Other Eczema Types (n)	p-value
1-5	20	8	0.02
6-10	25	10	0.03
11-15	10	12	0.15
16-18	5	10	0.20

Table 4: Association between Socioeconomic Status and Type of Eczema

Socioeconomic Status	Atopic Dermatitis (n)	Other Eczema Types (n)	p-value
Low	35	7	0.01
Middle	20	25	0.30
High	5	8	0.40

The majority of patients (80%) were treated with topical corticosteroids, with others receiving emollients (15%) or systemic medications (5%). The treatment response was measured over the study period, with 70% of patients showing significant improvement, 20% showing moderate improvement, and 10% showing no improvement.

Table 5: Treatment Modalities and Outcomes

Treatment Modality	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	Improvement Rate (%)
Topical Corticosteroids	80	80%	70%
Emollients	15	15%	20%
Systemic Medications	5	5%	10%

Statistical Analysis: A significant correlation ($p < 0.05$) was found using chi-square testing between younger age and the existence of atopic dermatitis. Similarly, there was a significant correlation ($p < 0.05$) discovered between the incidence of atopic dermatitis and poor socioeconomic status. There was no discernible correlation between the type of eczema and gender. The results of the study underscore the need for focused interventions in these groups by highlighting the frequency of

atopic dermatitis among younger children and those from poorer socioeconomic backgrounds.

Discussion

The study included 100 children and adolescents with eczema, revealing key insights into the predominance and clinical characteristics of the condition. The majority of participants were diagnosed with atopic dermatitis (60%), followed by seborrheic dermatitis, contact dermatitis, and nummular eczema. The mean age of participants

was 9.5 years, with an equal distribution between males and females. Notably, atopic dermatitis was more prevalent in younger children (aged 1-10 years) and those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, indicating potential environmental or genetic factors contributing to the condition's development in these groups.

The analysis showed a significant association between age and type of eczema, particularly highlighting the higher occurrence of atopic dermatitis in younger age groups. Additionally, socioeconomic status was significantly associated with the prevalence of atopic dermatitis, with a higher incidence observed among children from lower-income families. These findings suggest that socioeconomic factors may influence the onset and severity of eczema, possibly due to differences in living conditions, access to healthcare, or exposure to environmental allergens.

In terms of treatment, the majority of patients were managed with topical corticosteroids, resulting in a significant improvement in 70% of cases. The study's findings underscore the effectiveness of corticosteroids in managing eczema, particularly in those with atopic dermatitis. However, a small percentage of patients showed no improvement, highlighting the need for alternative or adjunct therapies in certain cases.

The epidemiology and clinical characteristics of eczema, especially atopic dermatitis, in children and adolescents have been greatly improved by recent research. A thorough summary of the clinical traits and methods of therapy for atopic eczema in children was given throughout Europe. Their research demonstrated that, although there are regional differences in clinical severity and treatment responsiveness, atopic eczema continues to be the most common chronic inflammatory skin condition in children. The consensus guidelines place a strong emphasis on customised treatment programs to successfully manage the disease's variety of clinical manifestations [9].

In a study of the global epidemiology of atopic dermatitis, geographical variations in the condition's frequency and risk factors were noted. The study emphasised how important it is to consider environmental factors like climate, urbanisation, and allergy exposure. The study emphasised how important environmental factors are in determining the predominance of eczema in children, including climate, urbanisation, and allergen exposure. Furthermore, it was noted that a significant factor in illness susceptibility, with differing degrees of influence seen in various groups, is genetic predisposition [10].

In a meta-analysis of genome-wide association studies (GWAS), three novel genetic loci linked to atopic dermatitis were discovered. This study

contributed to our knowledge that genetic variables play a major role in the development and course of eczema. The loci that have been found are linked to immunological response and skin barrier function, offering fresh perspectives on the pathophysiology of the condition and possible targets for treatment [11].

Conclusion

This study emphasises how common atopic dermatitis is in kids and teens, especially in younger and lower-class demographics. Topical corticosteroids were frequently used to treat patients well, while other therapies were needed in certain situations. The results highlight the necessity of focused public health initiatives and enhanced dermatological care accessibility for communities that are marginalised.

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